

tions. Gradual loading of the dental implant under conditions of increased occlusal load contributes to the prevention of its overload at the adaptation and rehabilitation stage and to the prolongation of the service life of the orthopedic structure as a whole.

3. Clinical observation of treated patients for three years indicates the clinical effectiveness of the proposed means and methods of treatment and the feasibility of their use in medical practice.

References:

1. Bida V.I., Struk V.I., Zabuga Yu.I. Patologichne stirannya zubiv i iogo likuvannya. –Chernivtsi: Bukrek, 2015. – 72s.
2. Fastovets' O.O. Kliniko-patogenetichne obruntuvannya kompleksnogo likuvannya-patologichnogo stirannya zubiv: avtoref. dis. ... d-ra

med. nauk: spets. 14.01.22 / O.O. Fasto-vets'. – K., 2008. – 35 s.

3. Mish K. E. Ortopedicheskoe lechenie s oporoi na dental'nye implantaty /Karl E. Mish; per. s angl. – M.:Rid Elsiver, 2010. – 616 s.: il.

4. Bida O.V. Osoblivosti ortopedichnogo likuvannya khvorikh iz chastkovoyu vtratoyuzubiv iz zastosuvannyam dental'noi implantatsii zalezchno vid pokaznikiv shchil'nosti kistkovoitkanini shchelepi // Ukraïns'kii stomatologichnii al'manakh. – 2016. – No 1 (tom 2). –S. 60–63.

5. Tkachenko I.M. Viktoristannya znimnoi shini-kapi dlya ortopedichnogo likuvannyapidvishchenoi stertosti zubiv, uskladnenoi yavishchami bruksizmu / I.M. Tkachenko // Bukovins'-kii medichnii visnik. – 2013. – T. 17, No 1 (65). – S. 129–133.

CLINICAL INDICATORS OF PROSTHETICS WITH ALL-CERAMIC PROSTHESES ON DENTAL IMPLANTS WITH SCREW AND CEMENT FIXATION

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7270522>

Musayeva H.

*Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, associate professor
Azerbaijan Medical University, Department of Orthopedic Dentistry
Baku, Azerbaijan*

Abstract

Orthopedic treatment of dental patients with dentition defects is one of the main tasks of dentistry, which improves the quality of life and prevents the development of complications of this pathology of local tissues and the body as a whole. Along with traditional methods of prosthetics (fixed bridge structures, partial and full dentures), designs based on dental implants are becoming increasingly popular. It due to a number of advantages of these prostheses, especially in conditions of distally unlimited defects in the dentition.

Keywords: dental implantation, fixed orthopedic constructions, ceramic restorations.

The accuracy of the connection of the implant with the abutment and the suprastructure as a whole is a fundamental factor in the stability of the future prosthetic construction. To ensure a reliable and high-quality connection between them, as well as the positional stability of the contacting elements, a guaranteed minimum gap between them with a strictly limited value is required [1]. One of the most important factors that ensure the reliability and duration of prosthetics on implants, in addition to surgical aspects, is the accuracy of fabricated structures and the mechanical integrity of all elements of the implant system [1]. The development of technologies for the manufacture of modern structures makes it possible to achieve a high accuracy of fit of the elements of the superstructure with a guaranteed minimum gap not exceeding 2–5 µm. In the absence of accuracy in the manufacture of the prosthesis and the presence of an uneven gap between the abutment and the inner surface of the orthopedic structure, conditions are created for the destabilization of the system with the appearance of areas of increased stress, which in turn results in de-cementing or weakening or destruction of the abutment fixing screw [1, 4]. Prosthesis are observed in the connection zone between the parts of the skeleton prosthesis, which, under cyclic loading, can lead to the destruction of the prosthesis frame in this area [2, 3]. According to other authors, in all-ceramic

restorations supported by dental implants, compressive and tensile stresses accumulate in the framework in areas that have an increased load, such as the cervical margin of the structure, where high torque and stress concentration arise as a result of the weighting effect [5]. These data are also confirmed by the results of electron microscopy of samples of all-ceramic structures after a cyclic load applied to them: rough areas, cracks, fractures, and chips are noted [6]. The study of the influence of the type of connection of structural elements on orthopedic structures, intraosseous dental implants, on the quality of orthopedic rehabilitation of patients and the duration of use of dentures is an important aspect of modern dentistry. However, today there is no consensus on this issue. The scientific literature provides convincing evidence for the benefits of both cemented and screw connections. Both types of constructs (cement-retained or screw-retained) affected the clinical outcome in different ways. None of the types of fixation had advantages. Cement-retained dentures showed more serious biological complications (implant loss, more than 2 mm bone loss), screw-retained designs had more technical problems. Screw-retained suprastructure undergoes easier removal than cemented, and therefore technical, respectively, biological complications are easier to treat. For these reasons, and due to the apparently higher biocompatibility, it is

these constructs that seem to be better. A more significant contribution is given to the correct positioning of the implant and a well-made prosthesis.

The method of cement fixation of orthopedic structures on implants has a certain imperfection due to the possibility of excess fixing material coming out with the subsequent development of inflammation in the tissues surrounding the dental implant, in the form of edema, pain, bleeding, exudation, bone loss in this area. In order to prevent such complications, it is recommended to use special fixing materials that make it easy to remove its excess without damaging soft tissues. One of the disadvantages of designs with screw fixation is the possibility of loosening, unwinding of the fixing screw under the action of chewing load.

According to clinical and laboratory data, ceramics has advantages over metal constructions: less discoloration of the mucosa, less plaque adhesion, low or no cytotoxicity, the quality of mucosal adhesion is similar to that of titanium. The high clinical efficiency of the use of all-ceramic prostheses based on dental implants has been proven in terms of technical, biological and optical aesthetic results of treatment with various implant systems of single-component ceramic structures with modeling of the anatomical shape of the crown directly on the zirconium abutment with subsequent screw fixation has some advantages over traditional cement-retained prostheses. The mean complication rate was 37.5% with fixation and 30% with screw-retained orthopedic structures. At the same time, in the case of cement fixation, complications were observed to a greater extent in the form of mucositis (14.87%), and in case of screw fixation, in the loosening of the fixing screw (20%).

A statistically significant difference between screw loosening and the presence of mucositis was obtained. Cemented restorations do not have the ability to unwind the fixation screw, but the presence of the fixation material increases the likelihood of soft tissue complications. At the same time, the incidence of mucositis and peri-implantitis with screw-retained prostheses is less than with cement-retained prostheses. Differences in the frequency of fractures and violation of the integrity of the structure in patients of both groups have not been determined [7]. Such complications can be avoided by using a monolithic all-ceramic supra-structure with a milled anatomical shape of the orthopedic structure.

Materials and methods.

The study of patients with defects in the dentition using non-removable all-ceramic structures of dentures based on intraosseous dental implants. All examined patients were diagnosed with unilateral or bilateral distally unlimited defects of the dentition (Kennedy class I and II). The control group consisted of 10 people of the same age without defects in the dentition, who underwent oral cavity sanitation. Patients were divided into two groups depending on the method of manufacturing the suprastructure and the type of its fixation. All patients underwent prosthetics based on osseointegrated dental implants installed using a two-stage technique.

The manufacture of orthopedic structures was carried out 3-4 months after the installation of dental implants. All-ceramic fixed dentures were made for patients of the first group (19 people) using a monolithic all-ceramic suprastructure with a milled anatomical shape of the patients, who used a two-component suprastructure: milled zirconium abutments and all-ceramic fixed dentures made according to traditional technology (20 people). The distribution of patients in the observation group was carried out taking into account the uniformity of representation by age, gender, type, quality of bone tissue, topography, and the defect of the dentition in each of them to level the possible influence of additional research factors.

To assess the condition of the surrounding soft tissues in the area of implants, the Schiller-Pisarev test was used at the stage of preparation for surgery, on the 10th day, 1 month, 6 and 12 months after the implant was placed. The dynamics of bone resorption in the area of the implant neck was determined according to the data of X-ray examination methods by determining the distance from the implant platform to the place of its contact with the bone tissue 3, 6 and 12 months after implant placement. The assessment of the hygienic state of the oral cavity and the presence of changes in the surrounding soft tissues was carried out by determining the plaque index (PI) (Silness-Löe), the PMA index (according to Parma) before the treatment, 3, 6 and 12 months after the installation of intraosseous dental implants. The determination of the clinical effectiveness of orthopedic treatment was carried out according to the criteria for assessing the quality of restorations: compliance of the orthopedic design with aesthetic requirements; edge adaptation; discoloration is clear around the edge of the crown; inflammation of the ash edge; ash region recession; decementation of the orthopedic structure; chipping and destruction of orthopedic structures; unwinding the fixing screw of the abutment; destruction (fracture) of the fixing screw.

Research results and discussion

Orthopedic rehabilitation was carried out in 39 patients who were diagnosed with defects in the dentition (Kennedy class I, II). After 3 months and in subsequent periods of observation, the stability indicators of the groups tended to increase and averaged: 66.02±0.61 units. after 3 months, 68.53±0.42 units after 6 months and 69.75±0.51 units. They did not differ statistically significant ($p > 0.05$) in patients of groups I and II. 2.12±0.015 points. One month after the operation, the results of the Schiller-Pisarev test indicated a decrease in inflammatory manifestations in the implantation zone in all observation groups: 2.51±0.019 points in group I, 2.53±0.022 points in group II ($p > 0.05$). Positive dynamics in all patients was observed in comparison with preliminary data.

Statistically significant data were obtained 3-4 months after implant placement in groups I and II (2.35±0.023 and 2.51±0.022 points, respectively, $p < 0.05$). During this period, the installation of orthopedic structures took place in accordance with the methods selected for patients in each of the observation groups. The results of the Schiller-Pisarev test after 6 months in group I amounted to 2.21±0.008 points and did not statistically significantly differ from those in

group II - 2.28 ± 0.022 points ($p > 0.05$). Thus, 6 months after implantation, patients of groups I and II showed no signs of inflammation. A similar trend remained a year after implantation: in group I, the indicator averaged 2.19 ± 0.043 points, in group II - 2.25 ± 0.023 points ($p > 0.05$). According to the X-ray methods of examination, there was no statistically significant difference in the indices of bone tissue resorption during the observation period in groups I and II: 0.535 ± 0.012 and 0.542 ± 0.01 mm after 3 months, 0.592 ± 0.007 and 0.601 ± 0.007 mm after 6 months. 0.728 ± 0.01 mm one year after implant placement, respectively. Also, there was no difference in the dynamics of bone loss around implants, depending on the method of fixation of orthopedic structures. Löe) it was found that in patients of both observation groups before the start of treatment, the indicators were within the normal range and amounted to 0.28 ± 0.04 and 0.30 ± 0.06 in groups I and II; and also in the control group - 0.20 ± 0.01 , respectively (Table 1).

After installing all-ceramic orthopedic structures and using them for 6 months, the average values of the plaque index in patients of group I remained almost at the same level and did not significantly differ from the average values of the index of patients in the control group ($p > 0.05$). At the same time, in group II, a statistically significant increase in the average values of this indicator was registered after 12 months of observation (0.38 ± 0.09 ; $p < 0.05$) compared with the indicators of group I in the same period. Before the start of treatment, the average values of RMA in patients of groups I and II of observation were, respectively, 25.1 ± 0.21 in group I and $26.5 \pm 0.33\%$ in group II and did not differ statistically significantly from each other ($p > 0.05$), however, there was a statistically significant difference compared with the control group ($7.0 \pm 0.81\%$) ($p < 0.05$), which was observed during the entire treatment period (Table 2). After 3 months of using all-ceramic non-removable structures based on dental implants in patients of group I, where prosthetics using a monolithic all-ceramic suprastructure with a milled anatomical shape of the orthopedic structure and screw fixation, there was a decrease in 0 values and their stability compared to the index values during installation. A moderate increase in the PMA index in patients of group II, who used a two-component suprastructure: milled zirconium abutment-ite and all-ceramic fixed dentures made by traditional technology, 3 months after fixation of orthopedic structures compared with the indices of group I ($p < 0.05$), can be explained by the creation of favorable conditions for the accumulation of dental plaque when using cement fixation, which largely depends on the quality and type of fixing material, as well as compliance with the technology before its use. After a year of observation, patients of group I showed a statistically significant difference in the PMA index compared to those in group II, which can also be explained by the difference in the hygienic condition of patients in these groups, associated with the configuration and method of fixation of orthopedic structures. It has been clinically proven that the use of non-removable all-ceramic structures supported by intraosseous dental implants using a monolithic all-ceramic suprastructure with a milled anatomical shape of the orthopedic structure and screw fixation compared to traditional ones has been clinically proven.

The results of this study confirmed the feasibility of using monolithic all-ceramic restorations based on dental implants due to the possibility of their more accurate execution using modern digital methods.

Conclusions.

Prostheses based on dental implants have shown that a monolithic all-ceramic suprastructure with a milled anatomical shape of the orthopedic structure and screw fixation has a high clinical efficiency, provides long-term rehabilitation and reduces the risk of complications during prosthetics. The clinical effectiveness of the use of modern technologies, the manufacture of non-removable orthopedic structures with resistance to dental implants will make it possible to make an informed choice of the prosthetics technique and the type of connection of the structural elements of the implant system, depending on the clinical situation, to prevent the occurrence of complications

References:

1. Bederak L.B. Vlijanie mnogokratnogo ispol'zovanija jelementov suprastruk-tur implantacionnyh sistem na kachestvo i nadezhnost' ortopedicheskikh konstrukcij na implantaty / L.B. Bederak, S.P. Rubnikovich, V.Ch. Den' // Stomatolog, –Minsk, 2015. – № 4 (19). – S. 50–5
2. Glossarij osnovnyh ponjatij, terminov, opredelenij i zavisimostej v bio-mehanike primenitel'no k cheljjustno-licevoj hirurgii i stomatologii / A.N. Chujko, R.A. Levandovskij, A.B. Belikov i dr. // Bukovinskij medicinskij vestnik. – 2012. – T. 16, № 2 (62). – S. 201–212.
3. Ershov S.A. Matematicheskij i jeksperimental'nyj analiz cel'nokeramicheskikh konstrukcij zubnyh protezov / S.A. Ershov, P.P. Brehlichuk, O.V. Klitinskaja // Vestnik UzhNU. Serija "Medicina". – 2010. – Vyp. 3(42). – C. 77–83.
4. Sirenko O.F. Jeksperimental'noe modelirovanie naprjazhenno-deformirovannogo sostojanija nes#emnoj ortopedicheskoy konstrukcii s oporoj na dental'nyj implantat i abatmenta metodom konechnykh jelementov / O.F. Sirenko // Sovremennaja stomatologija. – 2015. – № 4 (78). – S. 106–110. CAD/CAM-fabricated implantsupported restorations: systematic review / S. Бертольд, М. Патцельт, B.C. Spies et al. // Clin. Oral Impl. Res. – 2015. – Vol. 26(Suppl. 11). – P. 77–85. doi: 10.1111/clr.12633.
5. Cemented and screw-retained implant reconstructions: systematic review of the survival and complication rates / I. Sailer, S. Muhlemann, M. Zwahlen et al. // Clin. Oral Implants Res. – 2012. – Vol. 23 (Suppl. 6). – P. 163–201. doi: 10.1111/j.1600-0501.2012.02538.
6. Cemented and screw-retained implant-supported single-tooth restorations in the molar mandibular region: A retrospective comparison study po observation period of 1 to 4 years / A. Ferreira, M. Pesararocha-Diogo, G. Pradnes et al. // J. Clin. Exp. Dent. – 2015. – Vol. 7(1). – P. 89–94.
7. Cutrim E.S. Развитие нежных тиражей за один нулевой аппарат в Anterior Maxilla Restored With Cemented and Screw-Retained Crowns / E.S. Cutrim, D.C. Peruzzo, B. Benatti // Journal of Oral Implantology. – 2012. – Vol. 38, N. 6. – P. 700–705